

“TREES”: AN ARTISTIC-SCIENTIFIC OBSERVATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

In our research project «trees: Rendering ecophysiological processes audible» we connected acoustic emissions of plants with ecophysiological processes and rendered audible natural phenomena that aren't normally noticeable in an artistic way. The acoustic emissions of a tree in the Swiss Alps were recorded with special sensors, and all other non-auditory ecophysiological measurement data (e.g. the trunk and branch diameters that change depending on water content, the sap flow rate in the branches, the water present in the soil, air moisture, solar radiation, etc.) were sonified, i.e. translated into sounds. The recordings and sonified measurements were implemented in a number of different media art installations, which at the same time served as a research environment, in order to examine and experiment artistically with the temporal and spatial connections between plant sounds, physiological processes and environmental conditions in an artistic-scientific observation system.

1. INTRODUCTION

The link between trees and various climatic processes is usually not immediately apparent. Trees and plants do not live merely on moisture from rain, sunlight (which drives gas exchange) and nutrients from the soil: they absorb carbon dioxide from the air and produce the oxygen that we breathe, maintaining our climate and biosphere [1]. Gathering ecophysiological data by measuring the local climatic and environmental variables and the physiological processes within a plant in response to changes in these variables has become an important method to investigate the relationship between climate change and vegetation dynamics [2]. It helps to determine physiological thresholds of plants in terms of increasing temperature and consequently drought stress.

The Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) in Valais, a valley in the inner Swiss Alps, has experienced high mortality rates for some decades now: this phenomenon is believed to be caused *inter alia* by the effects of climate change, e.g. longer drought periods [3]. A downy oak (*Quercus pubescens*), for example, is better able to withstand the current climatic conditions whereas the Scots pine is pushed beyond its physiological limits despite the fact that both tree species have coexisted there

Figure 1. Scots pine forest in Salgesch/VS.

for thousands of years [4]. Consequently, a shift in the abundance of tree species is observed [5]. The ecophysiological knowledge acquired is used to explain the underlying processes: Hence the interest in cooperation between a biologist and an artist to study and depict the complex relationship between tree physiology and the climate on one hand and to explore the possibilities of acoustic and artistic representations of ecophysiological processes in trees on the other. Rendering physiological processes audible (e.g. water transport or trunk diameter changes) allows us to identify and better understand plants' responses to climatic processes.

2. ACOUSTIC EMISSIONS OF PLANTS AND DROUGHT STRESS

Plants emit sounds – a bigger part of these sounds are of transpiratory/hydraulic origin and are therefore related to

the circulation of water and air within the plant as part of the transpiration process [6]. The frequencies of the acoustic emissions lie mostly in the ultrasonic range (UAE = ultrasonic acoustic emissions), depending on the species-specific characteristics of the plant tissue [7]. The loudest UAE that occur in a plant arise due to drought stress. The excessive water tension in the water-conducting system leads to a collapse of single water columns in the plant vessels. They embolize, and this event releases an impulse that travels as an elastic wave through the tissue and may be detected as an UAE on the plant surface [8].

Figure 2. Sonogram of a Scots Pine: Ultrasonic acoustic emissions (UAE) appear as vertical spikes with different extents.

Thirsty and stressed plants make an inaudible noise [9]. UAE from plants lead to conclusions on their state and on the environmental conditions. Measurements of the amount and temporal occurrence of UAE are being used in ecophysiology to assess a plant's vulnerability to drought stress. More and longer occurring UAE in a plant are an indicator of increasing stress and desiccation. During our research project it became clear that our observation system could make a fundamental phenomenon tangible: namely, how plants react to ever-longer periods of heat and drought in the course of climate change.

When growth begins in spring, the tree benefits for a while from the water reserves from the winter that are still in the soil. However, the many acoustic emissions that occur already in spring (during the growth period) reveal a situation of immense stress in which the tree exists, because it must maintain the necessary turgor pressure in the cells in order to grow. If the water reserves in the soil have been exhausted, and there has been no precipitation in the meantime, the tree reacts by restricting its transpiration and growth (indicated by a vanishing of the UAE), in order to protect itself from dehydration. If periods of heat and drought become ever-longer as a result of climate change, trees will become susceptible to diseases and parasite infection – and will die early.

The acoustical measurement equipment we used for detecting and measuring the UAE consisted of a combination of UAE sensors from non-destructive testing (Vallen Systems VS150-M) with devices from bioacoustical research, the field of investigation of

acoustic behavior of animals (modified hydrophone preamplifiers, high sampling rate audio interfaces and adapted measuring/recording software, all by Avisoft). We have built also our own acoustic sensors, based on DIY technology like those used in many artistic experiments and performances: a copper wire pin was soldered onto a piezo element, in order to be able to couple them optimally into the tissue of a plant (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Self-built piezo needle sensor.

3. DATA SONIFICATION

The representation of data using sound (among other means) can help to exploit the effectiveness of our sense of hearing in grasping complex contexts both through immediate orientation in space and intuitive classification of sound characteristics [10]. Sonification offers a deep and broad insight into multidimensional data, enabling us to recognize patterns and providing an aesthetic and emotional experience of scientific discoveries. In contrast, many data sonification experiments in the scientific field are characterized by their shortcomings for inexperienced listeners. Very little weight is usually given to aesthetic judgments in the generation and use of sounds in scientific data sonification. What is mostly sought is simply a clear differentiation between individual sounds, which means that the artistic design of sonifications is usually rudimentary. Our aim was to increase the accessibility of our data sonification insofar as that we set it up from the very outset in accordance with musical criteria, i.e. the biological connections and correlations corresponded with the harmony, dramaturgy and emphasis of the artistically arranged sounds. By these

means a generative piece of music was created that is controlled by the data flows used, and which gathers together the individual processes and phenomena in a holistic musical experience.

The recorded plant signals were transposed into the audible range (audification) [11] and are played as an audio sample in the sonification system. The sounds of the weather are also played as a sample (wind and rain). All non-auditory measurement data have been sonified, i.e. measurement data series of individual physiological processes control the characteristics of individual sounds (parameter mapping) [12].

The different sonification modules are implemented in a Max/MSP patch, which replays measurement data from spring until summer 2015. For an adequate (temporal) experience of the most important processes, the speed of the running system is increased up to 36 times the normal speed, i.e. the 10-minute measuring intervals. Environmental data is mapped on the outer side of the spatial audio system of the *trees: Pinus sylvestris* installation (spatial audio versions), while tree data is played back on single speakers of the system, according to the spatial position and geographic orientation of the sensors on the plant.

Figure 4. Data display of the sonification module of *trees: Pinus sylvestris*.

The sounds that we used to sonify the measurement data can be divided into two groups: field recordings (rain, wind and plant sounds) and synthetic sounds. A larger number of phenomena do not manifest themselves acoustically, and we created metaphorical sounds that portrayed a single phenomenon, for instance sunlight or air humidity, in the best way. For sunlight, for instance, we took a string-like sound; for air humidity, a transformed and filtered burbling sound of a creek. All sound sources have a specific static or dynamic location within the audio system. The sun sound moves across the firmament, from east to west; wind comes from varying directions, louder if strong, softer if weak. As the sun rises, transpiration within the tree starts, and sap flow noises become louder. When the diurnal course reaches its peak at noon, cavitation pulses start, later decreasing during the course of the afternoon. The following table

shows the measurement data, the sound characters that we associated with them and how they have been spatialized within the audio system (Tab. 1):

Measured data	Sound character	Playback parameters
Daylight [RGB brightness]	Atmospheric synthetic sound	Amplitude, controlled by video brightness
Solar radiation [W/m ²]	String-like, synthetic sound	Amplitude
Sun position [azimuth, elevation]	Same	Spatial position
Air temperature [°C]	-	Main volume
Rel. air humidity [%]	Water-like, synthetic sound	Pitch, amplitude
Rain [mm]	Field rec.: Rain	Amplitude, spatial position
Wind [m/sec., azimuth]	Field rec.: Wind	Amplitude, spatial position
Soil water potential [kPa]	Field rec.: Seeping water	Amplitude, placed on discretely driven speakers near ground
Tree branch diameter [μm]	-	High pass filter, applied on sap flow sound
Tree sap flow [g H ₂ O/h]	Floating water, transposed up and filtered	Amplitude, placed on discretely driven speakers
Tree UAE	Field rec.: UAE	Pitch, amplitude, placed on discretely driven speakers

Table 1. Measurements and assigned sounds.

4. TREES: PINUS SYLVESTRIS

After a first prototype [13], we developed four versions of our artistic-scientific observation system *trees: Pinus sylvestris* until now. The *stereo/IP cam version* for two speakers and/or three headphones and three TFT monitors, the larger *spatial audio installation* (Fig. 5) and the adaption for ICST's *Immersive Lab* (Fig. 6) [14], as well as the adaption for ICST's *FlowSpace* [15]. The same sonification algorithms are implemented in all versions but are differently mapped on the speakers/headphones and present different video footage. In the stereo version, we used video footage from two IP cams on the stem of our measurement tree, each focusing on a branch of the plant.

The spatial audio system consists of an octagon carrying 36 self-built omni-directional speakers. It is designed as an accessible three-dimensional speaker array, where virtual sound sources are moved and placed within a defined space, and listeners can walk around inside the

system. The speaker matrix that we have developed is a hybrid sound system:

Figure 5. Spatial audio version of *trees: Pinus sylvestris*.

An Ambisonics [16] sound field is mapped onto the tube matrix, but some of the speakers are driven discretely. A 24" touch screen at the centre makes the installation an explorative, self-explanatory artistic system: The visitor is able to switch sound sources on and off to identify individual phenomena and their sonifications (see Fig. 4). A time-lapse video of the tree and its surroundings informs the visitor visually about the local climatic conditions (weather, time of day and light intensity). These images were taken by a so-called tree canopy camera, i.e. a fish-eye camera system that biologists use for measuring the light intensity coming through a canopy to investigate a tree's state of health or the light exposure of plants growing on the forest floor for instance. Furthermore, visitors may observe a graphic representation of the local climatic measurements and the correlations between the individual phenomena as well as a graphic display of the peak frequencies of the measured acoustic emissions at different locations along the plant's trunk and branches.

Figure 6. *trees: Pinus sylvestris* for the *Immersive Lab*.

The adaption for ICST's *Immersive Lab* (Fig. 6) marks an important shift regarding immersion. The projection surfaces of the system are touch sensitive: This enables the visitor to touch single branches of the tree, hear the branch-related acoustic emissions immediately and see a graphical representation of the local measurement data.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Our research project demanded of each participant to engage deeply with the mindset of the other disciplines involved in the project, in order to be able to develop a scientifically usable and artistically appropriate system that would make the key processes behind plant sounds identifiable and tangible. Aesthetic questions therefore already determined the structure of the experiment, for example where and how the cameras should be installed on the tree, or how the ecophysiological sensors should be mounted in order to enable an adequate and comprehensive presentation of the life processes and environmental conditions in an immersive environment. On the artistic side, consideration had to be made of the scientific and technological conditions; beyond this, the core artistic task was to develop adequate sonic representations of the non-auditory ecophysiological processes.

The reconstruction and staging of the life processes and environmental conditions of a tree in an artistic-technical environment has led to a completely new field of research and design for all those involved, with an innovative instrument: correlations of measured values and patterns in natural processes become aesthetic effects – abstract measurement data are reflected in images and sounds. The image of nature produced with digital technology demands an artistic nuancing of the acoustic and visual presentations, so that, for example, the variety of sounds present in the system do not disturb or overlap each other. Therefore, data must be interpolated and filtered, in order to be able to experience individual processes.

Another important point in our project emerged ever more clearly during the research work. The project *trees* dealt with the production of a new form of holistic knowledge that is not conveyed merely via the verbalisation of findings in a research report, but rather in a directly tangible auditory and visual (medial) form. The intention of the implementation of our artistic-scientific observation system was to create an all-encompassing experience from very different and complex data sets, and thus to draw a holistic picture of the life processes and environmental conditions of a tree that is under pressure from changing climatic conditions. The balance between the knowledge and practices applied is key – the artistic imagination of scientific objects must receive the same attention as the scientific foundation of the aesthetic objects.

The great success of the project in the media and among political representatives is due to the fact that we have

managed, in an artistic-scientific manner, to make it possible to grasp processes that are not usually noticeable and thus create a multifaceted, direct and comprehensive experience of natural phenomena. Our image of nature, in particular our perception of the plant kingdom, is still dominated by a perspective that treats life processes like the mechanistic functions of inanimate objects. Yet the animate object often reveals itself only by means of a change in perspective, a reduction in distance and the suspension of differences (between human subjects and natural objects). Present-day media technologies place us in a position to experience and interpret nature and natural objects and processes anew, in an immersive situation.

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